

Supporting Information

**Hybrid Enzyme-Electrocatalyst Cascade Modified Gas-Diffusion
Electrodes for Methanol Formation from Carbon Dioxide**

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Hybrid Enzyme-Electrocatalyst Cascade Modified Gas-diffusion Electrodes for Methanol Formation from Carbon Dioxide

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Experimental Section

Chemicals and Materials

All chemicals were of laboratory grade or higher and used without further purification. Potassium dihydrogen phosphate, di-potassium hydrogen phosphate trihydrate, methanol, and potassium chloride were obtained from VWR Chemicals. Poly(ethylene glycol)diglycidyl ether (PEGDGE, $M = 400 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$) was from Polysciences. Polyethyleneimine (PEI, average $M = 600 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$), polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) powder, alcohol dehydrogenase (ADH, 364 U mg^{-1} solid, EC 1.1.1.1), horseradish peroxidase (HRP, type VI-A, $\geq 250 \text{ U mg}^{-1}$ solid, EC 1.11.1.7), and alcohol oxidase (AOX, $70.7 \text{ mg protein mL}^{-1}$, EC 1.1.3.13) were from Sigma-Aldrich. β -nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NAD^+) and its reduced form (NADH) were from GERBU. Diaphorase (DIA, 841 U mg^{-1} , EC 1.6.99.-) and formaldehyde dehydrogenase (FaDH, 4 U mg^{-1} , EC 1.2.1.46) were from Creative Enzymes. Formic acid and formaldehyde were from J.T. Baker. All solutions were prepared using deionized water ($\rho = 18 \text{ M}\Omega \text{ cm}$) from a water purification system (SG Water).

The viologen-modified redox polymer poly(3-azido-propyl methacrylate-co-glycidyl methacrylate)-1-(hex-5-yn-1-yl)-1'-methyl-[4,4'-bipyridinium] ($\text{coP}(\text{N}_3\text{MA-GMA})\text{-vio}$) was synthesized as described elsewhere.^[1] The cobaltocene redox polymer, consisting of a cobaltocene derivative bound to branched polyethylenimine (BPEI-[CoCp₂]) was synthesized according to.^[2] The zwitterionic polymer poly(2-methacryloyloxyethyl phosphorylcholine-co-glycidyl methacrylate) (MPC) was synthesized as described in.^[3] The synthesis of Ag-Bi₂O₃ nanofibers has been reported in.^[4] The Os-complex modified redox polymer poly(1-vinylimidazole-co-allylamine)-[Os(2,2'-bipyridine)₂Cl]Cl (P-Os) was synthesized and purified as described before.^[5]

Electrode Modification

Before modification, glassy carbon disk electrodes ($d = 3 \text{ mm}$, CH Instruments) were cleaned by polishing with Al₂O₃ slurries of different grain sizes following standard protocols. For the $\text{coP}(\text{N}_3\text{MA-GMA})\text{-vio/DIA}$ -modified electrode, $5.0 \mu\text{L}$ of a mixture of $1.25 \mu\text{L}$ $\text{coP}(\text{N}_3\text{MA-GMA})\text{-vio}$ (20 mg mL^{-1}), $1.25 \mu\text{L}$ DIA (20 mg mL^{-1}), $0.50 \mu\text{L}$ PEI (10 mg mL^{-1}), and $2.00 \mu\text{L}$ H₂O were dropped onto a glassy carbon electrode surface. For the BPEI-[CoCp₂]/DIA-modified electrode, $5.0 \mu\text{L}$ of a solution containing a mixture of $1.25 \mu\text{L}$ BPEI-[CoCp₂] (13.5 mg mL^{-1}), $1.25 \mu\text{L}$ DIA (20 mg mL^{-1}), $1.00 \mu\text{L}$ PEGDGE (10 mg mL^{-1}), and $1.50 \mu\text{L}$ H₂O were dropped onto a glassy carbon electrode.

For the MPC/ADH/BPEI-[CoCp₂]/DIA-modified glassy carbon electrode, the first BPEI-[CoCp₂]/DIA layer was composed of a mixture of $1.25 \mu\text{L}$ BPEI-[CoCp₂] (13.5 mg mL^{-1}), $1.25 \mu\text{L}$ DIA (20 mg mL^{-1}), $1.0 \mu\text{L}$ PEGDGE (10 mg mL^{-1}), and $1.50 \mu\text{L}$ H₂O. After incubation and drying for 2 h at room temperature, the electrode was modified with a second layer consisting of a mixture of $2.0 \mu\text{L}$ MPC (20 mg mL^{-1}), $2.0 \mu\text{L}$ ADH (20 mg mL^{-1}), and $1.0 \mu\text{L}$ PEI (10 mg mL^{-1}).

For the FaDH/DIA/BPEI-[CoCp₂]-modified glassy carbon electrode, a mixture of $0.50 \mu\text{L}$ FaDH (20 mg mL^{-1}), $1.25 \mu\text{L}$ DIA (20 mg mL^{-1}), $1.00 \mu\text{L}$ BPEI-[CoCp₂] (13.5 mg mL^{-1}), $1.00 \mu\text{L}$ PEGDGE (13.5 mg mL^{-1}), and $2.00 \mu\text{L}$ H₂O were dropped on a glassy carbon electrode.

Hybrid Gas-Diffusion Electrode

The fabrication of the hybrid biocatalyst/Ag-Bi₂O₃ gas-diffusion electrode (GDE) for the CO₂ reduction cascade (Figure S1a) comprised the following steps. A hydrophobic carbon paper gas diffusion layer (H23C2, Freudenberg) was treated subsequently with acetone and $1.0 \text{ M H}_2\text{SO}_4$ in an ultrasonication bath and cleaned by rinsing with water and ethanol. The carbon paper was modified by drop casting with a mixture of $2.0 \text{ mg Ag-Bi}_2\text{O}_3$ and 1.0 mg PTFE powder in 2.0 mL ethanol. The GDE prepared in this way was placed in a specifically designed electrochemical cell. A pair of polypropylene gaskets were 3D-printed ensuring the exposure of a defined electrode area and avoiding electrolyte leakage (Figure S1b). The carbon paper coated with the Ag-Bi₂O₃ catalyst was placed in the center of the gasket with a piece of copper tape attached for electrical contact. A piece of carbon cloth (FE010694, Frontis Energy), which was later used as the substrate for enzyme immobilization, was placed over the modified carbon paper. The complete assembly was then positioned between two thick metal plates and placed in an oven at $210 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 12 min. In this way, the gaskets melted together, sealing all other components (Figure S1c). To prevent an uncontrollable deformation of the gasket, a scaffold made of poly(methyl methacrylate) was used to support the structure during the heat-treatment process (Figure S1d,e). The exposed electrode area in the final assembly was a circle with a diameter of 4 mm (area: 0.126 cm^2). For the modification with biocatalysts, $10.0 \mu\text{L}$ of a polymer/enzyme mixture composed of $2.5 \mu\text{L}$ DIA (20 mg mL^{-1}), $1.0 \mu\text{L}$ FaDH (20 mg mL^{-1}), $1.5 \mu\text{L}$ BPEI-[CoCp₂] (13.5 mg mL^{-1}), $2.0 \mu\text{L}$ PEGDGE (10 mg mL^{-1}), and $3.0 \mu\text{L}$ H₂O were dropped on the carbon cloth layer placed into the gasket. After incubation for 1 h at room temperature, the electrode was modified with a final layer consisting of a mixture of $4.0 \mu\text{L}$ MPC (20 mg mL^{-1}), $4.0 \mu\text{L}$ ADH (20 mg mL^{-1}), and $1.0 \mu\text{L}$ PEI (10 mg mL^{-1}). The complete assembly was then incubated at $4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ overnight before use.

Electrochemical Experiments

All electrochemical measurements were performed using a conventional three-electrode setup. The reference electrode consisted of a Ag/AgCl/3 M KCl electrode. All potentials are indicated with respect to the standard hydrogen electrode (SHE), considering a potential difference of 210 mV between Ag/AgCl/3 M KCl and the SHE. As counter electrode, a Pt wire was used. Phosphate buffer (0.1 M, pH 7.0) was used as electrolyte.

Measurements performed with enzyme-modified glassy carbon electrodes were carried out under an argon atmosphere using a sealed electrochemical cell. Measurements performed with the Ag-Bi₂O₃ GDE catalyst and the complete hybrid cascade system were done using a two-compartment flow-through cell. A fumasep cation exchange membrane (FKL-PK-130, Fumatech) was used to separate the working and counter electrode compartments. A CO₂ gas stream was supplied to the backside of the GDE at a flow rate of 20 mL min⁻¹. A N₂ gas stream was purged through the electrolyte compartment at a flow rate of 20 mL min⁻¹. The reported current densities were obtained by normalizing by the geometric electrode area.

Product Quantification

Formate concentrations were determined using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC; Dionex ICS-5000) with a diode array detector at 220 nm and a refractive index detector (RefractoMax520). An ion-exclusion column (Aminex HPX-87H, Bio-Rad) was used with 4 mM H₂SO₄ as eluent at an oven temperature of 70 °C.

For methanol detection, an alcohol biosensor was used consisting of alcohol oxidase (AOX) and horseradish peroxidase (HRP) embedded in an Os-complex modified redox polymer. The biosensor was prepared using a glassy carbon electrode (3 mm diameter) modified with a mixture of 2.0 μL AOX (20 mg mL⁻¹), 2.0 μL HRP (5 mg mL⁻¹), 1.0 μL P-Os (15 mg mL⁻¹), and 1.0 μL PEGDGE (10 mg mL⁻¹). Methanol detection with the biosensor was performed using an electrochemical cell open to the ambient atmosphere and equipped with a magnetic stirrer. An aliquot of 1.0 mL sample solution was added to 22.0 mL of electrolyte, consisting of 0.1 M phosphate buffer at pH 7.0.

Additional Figures

Figure S1. Assembly of the modified GDE for electrocatalytic CO₂ conversion. a) Schematic representation of the different elements involved in the assembly. b) Integration of the GDE in dedicated 3D-printed gaskets. c) Molten assembly ensuring confinement of the GDE, electrical connection, and a defined electrode opening size. d) Bespoke casing for preventing deformations during the melting step. e) Casing used during the melting procedure.

Figure S2. Structure of the two different redox polymers investigated for NADH regeneration using DIA. a) Viologen-modified redox polymer (coP(N₃MA-GMA)-vio). b) Cobaltocene-modified redox polymer (BPEI-[CoCp₂]).

Figure S3. Chemical structure of the zwitterionic redox polymer poly(2-methacryloyloxyethyl phosphorylcholine-co-glycidyl methacrylate) (MPC).

Figure S4. Influence of the electrolyte pH on the bioelectrocatalytic formaldehyde reduction using an electrode modified with ADH/MPC/DIA/BPEI-[CoCp₂]. Scan rate: 5 mV s⁻¹. Electrolyte: Ar-saturated 0.1 M phosphate buffer, containing 20 mM NADH and 10 mM formaldehyde.

Figure S5. Biocatalytic NAD^+ reduction using an electrode modified with ADH/MPC/DIA/BPEI-[CoCp₂], before (red trace) and after (blue traces) the addition of 20 mM formaldehyde. The arrow indicates the gradual decrease in catalytic current for successive cycles. Scan rate: 5 mV s^{-1} . Electrolyte: Ar-saturated 0.1 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.0.

Figure S6. Amperometric response of an electrode modified with FaDH/DIA/BPEI-[CoCp₂] in the presence of 2 mM NADH in solution at an applied potential of -690 mV vs. SHE . The red arrow indicates the addition of 0.5 mM formate. Electrolyte: Ar-saturated 0.1 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.0.

Figure S7. Cyclic voltammogram of a DIA/BPEI-[CoCp₂]/Ag-Bi₂O₃/GDE. Scan rate: 10 mV s^{-1} . Electrolyte: 0.1 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.0. A CO₂ gas stream was supplied to the backside of the GDE at a flow rate of 20 mL min^{-1} . A N₂ gas stream was used to saturate the electrolyte in the cathode compartment at a flow rate of 20 mL min^{-1} .

Figure S8. HPLC analysis of formate standard solutions with increasing concentrations (0.4, 1.6, 4.2, 7.8, and 9.8 mM) as indicated by the arrow.

Figure S9. a) Chemical structure of the Os-complex modified redox polymer (P-Os). b) Schematic representation of the enzyme-based alcohol biosensor for selective methanol detection. AOX: alcohol oxidase (enzyme structure based on the PDB entry 5I68^[6]), HRP: horseradish peroxidase (enzyme structure based on the PDB entry 1W4W^[7]).

Figure S10. Cyclic voltammograms of a glassy carbon electrode modified with AOX and HRP which are embedded together in a P-Os redox polymer, in the absence (black) and presence (red) of 500 μM methanol. Scan rate: 10 mV s^{-1} . Electrolyte: 0.1 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.0.

Figure S11. Methanol detection with the biosensor. Amperometric response of a glassy carbon electrode modified with AOX and HRP embedded in P-Os. Applied potential: 210 mV vs. SHE. Electrolyte: 0.1 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.0. The electrolyte solution was constantly stirred using a magnetic stirrer. Red arrows indicate the addition of methanol.

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